
THE HUMANITIES THROUGH ARCHITECTURE

Dr.P.Meenakumari ^{*1}

^{*1} Department of Architecture, SAP, Anna University, Chennai, India

Abstract:

Architecture has taken various impression and expression of what it is and its intent through the perspective of man, by the reflection of the place and its existence through time. The architecture being viewed as humanities was one progressive perspective by man, spanning from the period when buildings were erected in the past to the present. Architecture is a peculiar public art with buildings having a social function, and many buildings have public interface. The paper discusses architecture as discipline, which personifies man as the important entity and is define through primary humanistic disciplines philosophy, history, language, literature and theology .The appropriate conclusive contention is to view architecture through the atmosphere of humanities which affirms meaning and purpose to modern science, rather than merely comprising a series of supplementary fields of intellectual enquiry, alongside with scientific counterparts.

Keywords: Architecture; Humanities; Art and Science; Fundamental.

Cite This Article: Dr.P.Meenakumari. (2018). “THE HUMANITIES THROUGH ARCHITECTURE.” *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 5(2), 190-193. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1188679.

1. Introduction

For Architecture, buildings and built structures are embodiment and identity of the people, the place and the time .Through centuries and decades, Architecture has taken various impression and expression of what it is and its intent through the perspective of man, the reflection of the place and its existence spanning through time. The architecture being viewed as humanities was one primal perspective by man, spanning from the period when buildings were erected in past to present. This perspective is concurrent to Architect Arne Jacobsen statement ‘if a building becomes architecture, then it is art’ while Julia Morgan affirmation that view by stating ‘Architecture is a visual art, and the building speak for themselves’. Architecture is reviews as works of art – that completes the purpose of architecture. The art of the building is not in the visual appeal of the façade or the intrinsic detailing, but rather possessing the rare quality of drawing oneself to the buildings, making the living place more livable, filled with life.

2. Space of the Place

Architecture is a mixture of art and technique. This implies that the architect deals not only with artistic expression and aesthetics quality of the space in built place, but also the engineering

aspects that can be easily quantified and thereafter processed. Expressions such as light room, large space are some of fundamental aspect of architecture which provides the sense of positioning in the environment. Space is the feeling understood in the positioning of things, in experiencing the sense of living in the environment, also with dynamics and liberty of movement while moving between space either explorative or on through the paths of directives. The understanding of place is through experiencing the space of the place which in turn has to be experienced based on the sensation spend through sensory perception. The sensory perception of the man, through his sight, touch, smell and sound are able to comprehend and respond to the spatial quality of the built place. Through his senses, man is capable to scale his comfort, likes, sense of belonging and preferences in the built places which eventually of may manipulate and alter the character or personality of the people.

3. Humanities and Science

Ciriaco Moron Arroyo's states the significance and relevance of the humanities in the era of technology which provides a view point in the understanding of the role of the humanities in architecture. The criticism of the all-too-familiar assumption that the humanities serve as a resisting force against the growing domination of science and technology would seem to find some grain of truth in the discipline of architecture, with its interrelated and interdependent fields of enquiry. Arroyo states "It is hypocritical or naïve to defend the humanities as a bulwark against science and technology. The humanities, far from opposing them, are the halo that showers them with meaning and which receives meaning from their efforts".

From the many influences and references that contribute towards the development of design ideas, and their translation into built form, architecture is in every sense a practice that demands negotiation and dialogue between the full spectrum of practical, theoretical, social, political, cultural and technological concerns. It would be worth reminding ourselves of Vitruvius's famous assertion that the architect should be accomplished in a range of skills and have a wide field of knowledge – from moral philosophy to the laws of motion. Against the backdrop of the modern technological age, with the increasing emphasis on material and environmental aspects of sustainability, the scientific outlook has tended to have the upper hand. We need only appreciate the role of new technologies, in the modern age, in addressing social needs and achieving aesthetic effects.

4. Fundamentals for Architecture

The architect's professional life is perhaps more difficult than that of any other artist. When in expression of art work, an painter or sculpture can explore , modulate and create work in flection to his/her thoughts or action, but in the architect profession, the expression of the building reflecting the humanity value, through the creation of the architect which has the harder part of people acceptance based on the collective or subjective perspective. Architecture is a peculiarly public art because buildings generally have a social function, and many buildings have public interface. More than other artists, the architects must consider the public- their needs, preference and acceptance as on the moment and also for the future.

As per Arroyo understanding, the discipline in architecture personifies man as the important entity whose is looked as the whole in the context of place and time. So, it is irrefutable that the primary humanistic disciplines philosophy, history, language, literature and theology define the Architecture. Through the five disciplines expounded by Arroyo, we are given the keys to understanding and reflecting upon our own humanity by recognizing both our limitations and our potential to exceed ourselves. At the same time, the five disciplines indicate various modes of enquiry that give orientation and purpose to social, political, religious and cultural order. This sense of directionality of the humanities is important when considering questions of meaning in architecture, where material, spatial, topographical and symbolic aspects combine to convey ritual purpose to human existence. It is this metaphorical exchange between architectural and textual/verbal meanings that has provided the basis of architectural creativity throughout the ages.

5. The Necessities of Architecture

For the architecture to be read in terms of humanities, the architects are to perform the role of varied professionals or act as psychologists, sociologists, economists, businesspeople, politicians and others. They must also think like an engineers, for they must be able to construct structurally stable buildings and also have to take into account four basic and closely interrelated necessities which would made the existence and persistence of the building longer. The technical requirements are utility, spatial relationships, and content. Of the four necessities, the technical requirements of a building are the most obvious. Buildings must stand (and withstand). Architects must know the material and their potentialities, how to put the materials together, and how the materials will work on a particular site. So architects are engineers but they are something more as well, they are artists too. Functional requirements of architects in architecture, is what is made most in making of the buildings, but also usually stand them in such a way that they reveal their function or use. There are beliefs that form must follow function, then form stands “for” the function; of its building, then conventional forms or structures are often sufficient. The next important necessity is that, spatial requirements of architecture -A building that is technically awry with poor lighting or awkward passageways or cramped rooms will distract from any artistic meaning, and so usually will a form that fails to reveal the function of its building, or a form that fails to fit into its spatial context.

6. Conclusion

More instructive and conclusive contention is to view humanities as an envelope or an atmosphere that affirms meaning and purpose to modern science, rather than merely comprising a series of supplementary fields of intellectual enquiry, alongside with scientific counterparts. This contention is based, of course, on the historical relationship between the humanities and science; that modern science emerged as a consequence of its more ancient fields of enquiry, principally philosophy and theology. It is also to note that in today’s context, the encompassing role for the humanities in the present age of information technology would seem to be groundless under the influences of materialistic reading, reflecting an outdated perspective of what has become a rapidly changing globalized culture. It is needed to examine the demise, evident in many aspects of contemporary society, of the various disciplines that constitute the humanities in contemporary culture to appreciate the grounds of this counter-argument. The pervasive

nature of popular (media driven) culture and mass consumption, with their obsessions with instant visual gratification and entertainment, has in many instances marginalized, or overshadowed the more reflective activities of the humanities. Architecture is as much a byproduct of this development as most other endeavors, resulting in greater emphasis being placed on the experiential nature of architectural aesthetics over and above questions of meaning.

References

- [1] Barwise, Jon; Perry, John 1983. *Situations and Attitudes*. Cambridge, London: MIT Press
- [2] Ciriaco Morón Arroyo and Ciriaco Morón Arroyo 2002, *The Humanities in the Age of Technology*, Catholic Universities of America Press.)
- [3] Davidson, Donald 1984. *Inquiries into Truth and Interpretation*. Oxford: Clarendon Press; New York.
- [4] Donoghue, Martin 1987. *The Language of Architecture*. – *Journal of Aesthetic Education*, Vol. 21 (3), pp. 53–67
- [5] Goodman, Nelson 1992. *How buildings mean*. – *The Philosophy of the Visual Arts*. Ed. Philip Alperson. New York, Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 368–376.
- [6] Scruton, Roger 1979. *The Aesthetics of Architecture*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- [7] Solà-Morales, Ignasi de 1996. *Present and futures: Architecture in cities*. – *Present and Futures: Architecture in Cities*. Eds. Ignasi de Solà-Morales, Xavier Costa. Barcelona: Col·legi d'Arquitectes de Catalunya, Centre de Cultura Contemporània de Barcelona,

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: meku67@ yahoo.co.in